

Beyond Censorship: An Inquiry into Public Interest in Journalism

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Public interest is accepted as one of the most important news value. This, coupled with a perception of journalism being unbiased and objective, invests journalism with unparalleled power of agenda setting and guiding public opinion. However, public interest is often compromised at the altar of other interests such as ideology and market. Despite the fact that there seems an a priori understanding of the concept of public interest, the definition and scope of public interest in journalism lacks a general consensus. This study based, on a survey of University students, tries to establish, from the audience perspective, what public interest in journalism should be.

Keywords: Journalism, Public Interest, Public Opinion

INTRODUCTION

Several functional values, referred to as news values, are used to evaluate the “newsworthiness” of a story. However, it is not a universally agreed list of news values but only a loose compilation of opinions; “public interest” is generally accepted to be one of the most important. However, journalism scholars and professionals lack a consensus on the definition and scope of public interest in journalism. In such a scenario, this study approaches the problem by trying to define the scope of public interest from the perspective of the audience – getting the consumers of news to identify what is *in* their interest.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Despite the unique privilege of being the agenda setters and drivers of public opinion, the public trust in journalism is abysmal. Ipsos MORI, Britain’s second largest market research organisation, has been tracking public trust in professionals through a poll in Britain since 1983. Yearly average of Ipsos MORI’s (2015) poll data on *Trust in professions*, conducted from 1983 to 2014 shows that less than 13 percent people trust journalists with telling the truth compared to 15 percent trusting politicians. The trust in journalists and politicians has consistently been the lowest, far lower than any other profession.

A Carnegie UK Trust study (2013) inquiry into what can be justified in the public interest, and how it can be justified revealed a “strikingly low trust in the ability of newspapers to operate in ways that people would consider to be ethical” (p.7). The respondents did not expect tabloids or even the country’s three biggest-selling dailies to ‘generally operate in an ethical manner, with due regard to the public interest’ (p.7). There seems an overall consensus on the need for public interest in journalism.

Public interest has been the most recurring theme in a number of ethical codes developed and prescribed by independent media organisations, associations and media regulators. The debate over public interest stems from the four basic, yet recurring, concerns in the practice of journalism – delimiting means and methods of procuring information and public’s right to information, and justification of infringement of privacy and defamation.

In their introduction to the principles and ethics Press Council of India (nd) advocates “the fundamental objective of journalism is to serve the people with news, views, comments and information on matters of public interest in a fair, accurate, unbiased, sober and decent manner” (para 0). Editor’s Guild of India (2007) *A Code of Practice for Journalists* cautions that the newspaper editors should “measure the right to publish against the relevant

“public interest” before according supremacy to the former” (np). The News Broadcasters Association, a body representing 54 news and current affairs channels in India, in its *Code Of Ethics & Broadcasting Standards* recommends “...the selection of items of news shall also be governed by public interest and importance based on the significance of these items of news in a democracy” (section 1, para 6) as comprising a fundamental principle. UK’s Independent Press Standards Organisation (IPSO) in its *Editors’ Code of Practice* (2015) attempts to define the scope of public interest as follows:

1. The public interest includes, but is not confined to:

- Detecting or exposing crime or serious impropriety.
- Protecting public health and safety.
- Preventing the public from being misled by an action or statement of an individual or organisation.

1. There is a public interest in freedom of expression itself. (IPSO, 2015, np)

The code further says that the editors are required to “demonstrate fully that they reasonably believed that publication, or journalistic activity undertaken with a view to publication, would be in the public interest and how, and with whom, that was established at the time” (IPSO, 2015, np).

Several media organisations have either adopted or adapted the code. *BBC’s Editorial Guidelines* reads like an elaboration of this code:

There is no single definition of public interest. It includes, but is not confined to:

- exposing or detecting crime
- exposing significantly anti-social behaviour
- exposing corruption or injustice
- disclosing significant incompetence or negligence
- protecting people’s health and safety
- preventing people from being misled by some statement or action of an individual or organisation
- disclosing information that assists people to better comprehend or make decisions on matters of public importance. (British Broadcasting Corporation, nd, p.65)

The guidelines further say, “There is also a public interest in freedom of expression itself” (British Broadcasting Corporation, nd, p.65).

In a landmark judgement in the case of *London Artists Ltd. v. Little*, 1968, Lord Denning (1969) states, “There is no definition in the books as to what is a matter of public interest. All we are given is a list of examples...” (p.391). The judgement, perhaps for the first time, goes on to define public interest as follows:

“Whenever a matter is such as to affect people at large, so that they may be legitimately interested in, or concerned at, what is going on; or what may happen to them or to others; then it is a matter of public interest...” (Lord Denning, 1969, p.391).

The definition was however not comprehensive. Moore (2007) describes how a public interest journalists act: “Public interest journalists find, digest and distil information that helps the public form views and make decisions.” For this, according to Moore, the journalist acts in two ways – first, acting as “a watchdog, holding the powerful to account, exposing fraud, deceit, corruption, mismanagement and incompetence,” and the second, through a discharge of “the responsibility to inform, explain and analyse” (Moore, 2007).

The Crown Prosecution Service laid down *Guidelines for prosecutors on assessing the public interest in cases affecting the media* in 2012. These guidelines were later notified and issued by the Director of Public Prosecutions on 13 September 2012. The guidelines while observing that “public interest served by freedom of expression and the right to receive and impart information has never been defined in law,” came closest to defining it through examples of conduct which is capable of serving the public interest:

- (a) Conduct which is capable of disclosing that a criminal offence has been committed, is being committed, or is likely to be committed.
- (b) Conduct which is capable of disclosing that a person has failed, is failing, or is likely to fail to comply with any legal obligation to which s/he is subject.
- (c) Conduct which is capable of disclosing that a miscarriage of justice has occurred, is occurring or is likely to occur.
- (d) Conduct which is capable of raising or contributing to an important matter of public debate. There is no exhaustive definition of an important matter of public debate, but examples include public debate about serious impropriety, significant unethical conduct and significant incompetence, which affects the public.

(e) Conduct which is capable of disclosing that anything falling within any one of the above is being, or is likely to be, concealed.

(Crown Prosecution Service, 2012, p.9)

The guidelines while cautioning that “each case must be considered on its facts and merits,” explains that the above list “is not intended to be exhaustive,” as also the absence of above factors does not imply that no public interest is served (Crown Prosecution Service, 2012, p.10).

Adherence to public interest is as important an ethical issue as it is legal. The codes, such as the one by CPS, may help prosecutors in establishing culpability in legal cases relating to infringement of privacy or defamation or disclosure of classified information, the day-to-day practice of journalism will continue to struggle with balancing right to receive and impart information with the underlying issues of privacy and defamation. The boundaries will continue to be stretched.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study is based on empirical data collected from the students in the Himachal Pradesh University campus. Students were invited to participate in the study through on-campus notices. Of the 88 students who enrolled for the study, only 79 respondents could be contacted. Of these only 40 reported any exposure to TV news. Only such respondents were included for the sample survey in this study. Thus, a final sample size of 40 was reached. The sample represents students from almost all faculties in the university. Data was gathered using an interview schedule. The schedule asked the respondents to rate on a five point Likert-type scale their perception (from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree) of the public interest

in journalism is served by conduct in concurrence with the six criteria laid down by CPS (2012).

The following hypotheses were tested:

H₁: There will be a significant difference in the number of respondents who believe that public interest in journalism is served by –

- a. conduct which is capable of disclosing that a criminal offence or anti-social behaviour has been committed, is being committed, or is likely to be committed.
- b. conduct which is capable of disclosing that a person has failed, is failing, or is likely to fail to comply with any legal obligation to which they are subject.
- c. conduct which is capable of disclosing that a miscarriage of justice has occurred, is occurring, or is likely to occur.
- d. conduct which is capable of raising or contributing to an important matter of public debate such as public health and safety, human rights, national interest, etc.
- e. conduct which is capable of preventing people from being misled by some statement or action of an individual or an organization.
- f. conduct which is capable of disclosing that anything falling within any one of the above is being, or is likely to be, deliberately concealed.

The data was tabulated and processed with the help of IBM SPSS Statistic 20. Goodness-of-fit Chi-square test was used for determining significance of percentages.

Table 1
Perception about criteria of Public Interest in journalism

Ro w	Criteria Public interest is in...	Percentage of respondents					Chi	df	Sig.
		SD	D	CS	A	SA			
1	disclosing crime or its possibility	12.5	22.5	5.0	45.0	15.0	18.750	4	.001
2	disclosing failure or its possibility	5.0	20.0	50.0	25	0.0	16.800	3	.001

	possibility								
3	disclosing injustice or its possibility	2.5	17.5	30.0	37.5	12.5	15.500	4	.004
4	contributing to public debate	7.5	10.0	7.5	50.0	25	26.750	4	.000
5	preventing misleading of public	5.0	17.5	32.5	40.0	5.0	20.250	4	.000
6	disclosing deliberate concealment	7.5	37.5	27.5	17.5	10.0	12.500	4	.014

SD: Strongly disagree; D: Disagree; CS: Can't say; A: Agree; SA: Strongly agree
Chi: Chi-square statistic; df: Degree of freedom; Sig.: Level of significance

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sample size of 40 consisted of 52.5 percent male and 47.5 percent female students. The largest number of respondents belonged to the sciences streams, namely, general science and computer science, making up for 52.5 of total respondents. Respondents from all other educational streams put together, namely, social science, laws, commerce and management, languages, performing and visual arts and education made for less than 50 percent of respondents. Approximately three-fourth respondents (i.e. 72.5%) belong to urban areas. A little over one-fourth (27.5%) belong to rural areas.

The response to each of the six items was tabulated separately and frequency and percentage of the respondents rating each item as 'strongly disagree', 'disagree', 'can't say', 'agree' and 'strongly agree' were calculated. These responses for all six items are presented in the table below. A goodness-of-fit Chi-square test was performed to analyse if there is a significant difference in

the percentage of respondents agreeing or disagreeing with a particular parameter constituting public interest in journalism.

As is clear from row 1 of Table 1, a significantly large number (60 percent) of respondents agree that public interest in journalism is served by actions capable of disclosing that a criminal offence or anti-social behaviour has been committed, is being committed, or is likely to be committed. Only 35 percent disagree or strongly disagree. The chi-square statistic is significant for difference between those who strongly disagree, disagree, are not sure, agree and strongly agree at 99 percent confidence level. Therefore, the test hypothesis H_{a1} is accepted. It can be claimed that most respondents agree that public interest in journalism is served by actions capable of disclosing that a criminal offence or anti-social behaviour has been committed, is being committed, or is likely to be committed.

Table 1, row 2 shows that a significantly large percentage (50 percent) of respondents are not sure if public interest in journalism is served by actions capable of disclosing that a person/organisation has failed, is failing, or is likely to fail to comply with any legal obligation to which they are subject. There are equal number of respondents who

agree or disagree with this parameter as a test of public interest in journalism. The chi-square statistic is significant for at 99 percent confidence level. Therefore, the test hypothesis H_{b1} is accepted. However, as equal number of respondents agree or disagree with this parameter, without deeper analysis it can't be claimed that intention to disclose that a person/organisation has failed, is failing, or is likely to fail to comply with any legal obligation is agreed or disagreed upon by most respondents as a constituting public interest in journalism.

As is clear from Table 1, row 3, a significantly large number (50 percent) of respondents agree or strongly agree that public interest in journalism is served by actions capable of disclosing capable of disclosing that a miscarriage of justice has occurred, is occurring, or is likely to occur. Only 20 percent respondents disagree or strongly disagree. The chi-square statistic is significant for at 96 percent confidence level. The test hypothesis H_{c1} is accepted. Therefore it may be deduced that that intention to disclose that a miscarriage of justice has occurred, is occurring, or is likely to occur is agreed upon by most respondents as a constituting public interest in journalism.

As per row 4 of Table 1, a significantly large number (75 percent) of respondents agree or strongly agree that public interest in journalism is served by actions capable of raising or contributing to an important matter of public debate such as public health and safety, human rights, national interest, etc. Only 17.5 percent disagree or strongly disagree. Others are not sure. The chi-square statistic is significant at 100 percent confidence level. Therefore, H_{d1} is accepted. So it can be claimed that most respondents agree that public interest in journalism is served by actions capable of raising or contributing to an important matter of public debate.

As is clear row 5 of Table 1, a significantly large number (45 percent) of respondents agree that public interest in

journalism is served by conduct which is capable of preventing people from being misled by some statement or action of an individual or an organization. However, 22.5 percent respondents disagree or strongly disagree with this. A significant numbers (32.5 percent) are not sure. The Chi-square test statistic is significant at 100 percent confidence level with 4 degrees of freedom. Therefore H_{e1} is accepted. Thus it may be concluded that most respondents agree that public interest in journalism is served by conduct which is capable of preventing people from being misled by some statement or action of an individual or an organization.

Table 1, row 6 shows a significantly large number (45 percent) of respondents either disagree or strongly disagree that public interest in journalism is served by conduct capable of disclosing that anything falling within any one of the above is being, or is likely to be, deliberately concealed. Only 27.5 percent respondents agree or strongly agree with this. A significant numbers (27.5 percent) are not sure. The Chi-square test statistic is not significant at 95 percent confidence level with 4 degrees of freedom. Therefore H_{f1} is rejected. Thus it may be concluded that from the above data it cannot be concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents agreeing or disagreeing with the parameter that public interest in journalism is served by conduct capable of disclosing that anything falling within any one of the above is being, or is likely to be, deliberately concealed.

CONCLUSION

The press is known as the Fourth Estate as it is expected to uphold and work in public interest. However, several factors such as ownership, market and political pressures, and other para-professional reasons smite the working of the press. As there is an absence of a general consensus on the definition or purview of public interest, various

professional organisations and researchers delineate public interest differently; yet they have a broad consensus on its nature. This study based on a sample survey of the students of Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla, finds that the students believe that public interest in journalism is served by conduct which is capable of: disclosing that a criminal offence or anti-social behaviour

has been committed, is being committed, or is likely to be committed; disclosing that a miscarriage of justice has occurred, is occurring, or is likely to occur; raising or contributing to an important matter of public debate; and preventing people from being misled by some statement or action of an individual or an organization.

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